

ATTRACTION OF *CNAPHALOCROCIS MEDINALIS* (GUENÉE) TO VOLATILES EMITTED FROM *MEGATHYRSUS MAXIMUS* (JACQ.)

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ABSTRACT

A study was carried out to unveil the potential volatiles emitted from guinea grass *Megathyrus maximus* (Jacq.). Observations were taken from inflorescence of guinea grass after sun set and number of adult rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) attracted per inflorescence were counted. To determine nutritional compounds and volatile hydrocarbon profile, surface chemicals and semiochemicals were extracted from guinea grass inflorescence and analysed using High-resolution Liquid Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (HR-LCMS) and Gas Chromatography- High-resolution Mass Spectrometry (GC-HRMS) respectively. The HR-LCMS results revealed the presence of an amadori compound called n-(1-deoxy-1-fructosyl) serine and the GC-HRMS results revealed 19 organic volatile compounds, among them six potential attractant compounds were identified. They are bis (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, di-n-octyl phthalate, diisooctyl phthalate, 1,2-benzenedicarboxylic acid, dinonyl ester, 4-methyl decane and phthalic acid 6-ethyloct-3-yl-2-ethylhexyl ester. The study has unveiled the leaf folder attractant in guinea grass is not just a single compound but a mixture of compounds.

Key words: Rice leaf folder, guinea grass, semiochemicals, SMW, HR- LCMS, GC-HRMS, rice, amadori compound, Tukey's method, ANOVA.

Rice is the most important staple food (Bin and Zhang, 2023; Wang et al., 2023), grown over an area of 165 million ha (FAO, 2018), with an annual production of 755.45 mt (FAO, 2021). India is the second largest producer of rice after China (Agriculture statistics at a glance, 2018). The paddy farmers in India are facing difficulties due to economic losses, the main one being due to insect pest, going up to 25% (Dhaliwal et al., 2010). Among these pests, the rice leaf folder, *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) is a serious pest. It attacks throughout the stages of growth from nursery to harvest, with relatively high incidence in the reproductive phase (Litsinger et al., 2006). The plants attacked by *C. medinalis* reduces photosynthetic capacity, particularly at the booting stage in flag leaves and leads to a loss of production (Padmavathi et al., 2013). According to Teng et al. (1993) *C. medinalis* can cause 63-80% yield loss in high yielding susceptible varieties. Use of chemical pesticides has proven to be an efficient way to manage *C. medinalis* (Huang et al., 2011; Zheng et al., 2011). Typically, deltamethrin, chlorpyrifos, and chlorantraniliprole are recommended (Chen and Klein, 2012; Yang et al., 2018). The widespread application of these has resulted in the emergence of resistance

(Endo et al., 1993; Xiao et al., 1994; Anbalagan and Regupathy, 2008). Use of sex pheromones to reduce lepidopteran pests has evolved now into a useful and effective method (Chen et al., 2014). In rice fields, *C. medinalis* sex pheromones have been extensively used and are now an important part of IPM programs (Kawazu et al., 2004, 2005; Litsinger, 2009; Cho et al., 2013; Byers, 2014; Chen et al., 2014). Traps based on sex pheromones are only effective against male *C. medinalis*. In the field condition the female to male ratio stands at 1:0.62 (Guo et al., 2019). It suggests that female comprise the majority and hence it is essential to target the females. It has been shown that plant-based semiochemicals found in food sources draw in both male and female (Gao et al., 2023). It has been observed that adult *C. medinalis* been getting attracted towards the inflorescence of *Megathyrus maximus*. This study focuses on the identification of volatile compounds responsible for attraction and the benefits gained by *C. medinalis*, thereby reducing the male and female population.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A random survey was conducted during 2021 to

study the activity of insect pests in rice field during night hours. During this, the incidence of *C. medinalis* on the inflorescence of *M. maximus* was noticed. To identify the cause of this attraction a study was conducted from August 20th to October 21st in 2022 and 2023. The observations were taken during evening hours ($28 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$, 65-- 75% RH) at the Institute of Agriculture Technology Regional Agriculture Research Station (IAT-RARS), Pattambi, Kerala, India (10.81°14'N, 76.19°03'E). All the adult stages of *C. medinalis* were recorded in open natural field condition, and number of adults/unit inflorescence were recorded once in a week on Standard Meteorological Week (SMW) basis. A total of 30 observations/ week were taken for 9 weeks from 34 SMW to 42 SMW using the help of LED lights. These observation data were analyzed using R-Studio (v4.1.2; R Core Team 2021). To determine whether the week has a significant effect on adult incidence and to assess whether this trend is consistent across years, a two-way ANOVA was conducted. The analysis included week as a factor and year as a second factor to test for differences between years. The ANOVA results indicates that the effect of weeks on the number of adult moths is significant.

To determine which specific weeks, differ significantly, a multiple comparison test was done using the Tukey's method. Behaviour of the moths on inflorescence were recorded using Nikon d5600 camera. Adult moths were collected from inflorescence for sexual trait evaluations. Morphological character of moths were compared with known descriptions (Varun, 2017; Gangwar, 2015). The *M. maximus* grains were collected from wildy grown plants. These samples were soaked in sterile water for 1 hr to dissolve the substances present on the surface of *M. maximus* at room temperature. After filtering the grains, this solution was used to assess the presence of different surface chemical on inflorescence and subjected to HR- LCMS analysis. The analysis was performed on an Agilent 6550 iFunnel Q-TOF LC/MS system equipped with Agilent 1290 Infinity UHPLC, 1260 infinity Nano HPLC system (Agilent Technologies, Kista, Sweden). Samples of inflorescence were collected from *M. maximus* and the samples were cleaned using sterile water in order to avoid any contaminants. The collected samples were extracted using HPLC grade hexane at room temperature. The extract was concentrated using rotary evaporator and used for the GC-HRMS analysis. Volatile hydrocarbon analysis was carried out on AccuTOF-GCv JMS-100GCv equipped with an Agilent 7890 GC (JEOL, Tokyo, Japan). The compounds in the

extract were identified by comparing the extract with the compounds from MS Database library, National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) based on their retention time and mass spectra.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Adult moths were observed to be attracted to the inflorescences of *M. maximus* located approximately 5 m away from the rice field (Fig. 1). This behaviour is observed only after sunset and the attraction was signaled by constant antennal swing, movement of proboscis through the surface of the grains and head movements. The moths were found to be more attracted towards mature inflorescence than newly emerged ones. A sticky substance was noticed on the surface of inflorescence and adult moths were found to be feeding on it. In addition, moths are observed to be neither disturbed nor attracted to the low intensity lights. The observations taken to record the incidence of *C. medinalis* on inflorescence when statistically analysed by two-way ANOVA got visualized as boxplot (Fig. 2); showing the distribution of adult counts across 9 standard meteorological weeks; and revealing that there is a similar pattern in both years; weeks significantly influenced the adult counts ($p < 2 \times 10^{-16}$) was well below the level of significance (0.05) (Table 1). Subsequently, a Tukey's post-hoc test was performed

Fig. 1. Female *C. medinalis* on inflorescence of *M. maximus*

Fig. 2. Adult moth incidence by week and year

Table 1. Result of two-way ANOVA and HSD test
 (No of adults as a function of week and year)

Source	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F	p Value
Week	8	305.30	38.16	75.098	<2e-16 ***
Year	1	1.67	1.67	3.280	0.0707
Week*Year	8	5.20	0.65	1.279	0.2518
Residuals	522	265.27	.51		

Tukey's HSD test

Weeks compared	Difference	Lower CI	Upper CI	p adj	Weeks compared	Difference	Lower CI	Upper CI	p adj
36-34	0.467	0.061	0.872	1.10E-02*	40-38	-0.967	-1.372	-0.561	2.70E-10*
37-34	1.667	1.261	2.072	2.54E-10*	41-38	-1.883	-2.289	-1.478	2.54E-10*
38-34	2.05	1.645	2.455	2.54E-10*	42-38	-2	-2.405	-1.595	2.54E-10*
39-34	1.517	1.111	1.922	2.54E-10*	40-39	-0.433	-0.839	-0.028	2.59E-02*
40-34	1.083	0.678	1.489	2.54E-10*	41-39	-1.35	-1.755	-0.945	2.54E-10*
37-35	1.55	1.145	1.955	2.54E-10*	42-39	-1.467	-1.872	-1.061	2.54E-10*
38-35	1.933	1.528	2.339	2.54E-10*	41-40	-0.917	-1.322	-0.511	4.68E-10*
39-35	1.4	0.995	1.805	2.54E-10*	42-40	-1.033	-1.439	-0.628	2.54E-10*
40-35	0.967	0.561	1.372	2.70E-10*	35-34	0.117	-0.289	0.522	9.93E-01 NS
37-36	1.2	0.795	1.605	2.54E-10*	41-34	0.167	-0.239	0.572	9.37E-01 NS
38-36	1.583	1.178	1.989	2.54E-10*	42-34	0.05	-0.355	0.455	1.00E+00 NS
39-36	1.05	0.645	1.455	2.54E-10*	36-35	0.35	-0.055	0.755	1.54E-01 NS
40-36	0.617	0.211	1.022	9.66E-05*	41-35	0.05	-0.355	0.455	1.00E+00 NS
42-36	-0.417	-0.822	-0.011	3.86E-02*	42-35	-0.067	-0.472	0.339	1.00E+00 NS
40-37	-0.583	-0.989	-0.178	3.10E-04*	41-36	-0.3	-0.705	0.105	3.41E-01 NS
41-37	-1.5	-1.905	-1.095	2.54E-10*	38-37	0.383	-0.022	0.789	8.06E-02 NS
42-37	-1.617	-2.022	-1.211	2.54E-10*	39-37	-0.15	-0.555	0.255	9.66E-01 NS
39-38	-0.533	-0.939	-0.128	1.58E-03*	42-41	-0.117	-0.522	0.289	9.93E-01 NS

***p<.005

to identify specific groups of weeks with significant and non-significant differences in adult counts. Among the significant weeks, the 38th week exhibited the highest mean adult moth count, indicating it as the peak period of moth incidence, and incidence increases gradually from 34 to 38 SMW, and after this gradually declined.

Based on morphological characters given by Varun (2017) and Gangwar (2015) sexing of adults was performed. The male has a wing span about 16-18mm with dark brown patch and shining, roconial scales along mid costa of forewing and cilia also brownish colour. Abdomen of male is ochreous and covered with scales and white towards pointed end. The anal tuft black, striped with white patches on both sides of anal extremity (Fig. 3). Whereas the female has a wing span of 18-19 mm; forewing triangular with costal and outer areas brownish yellow, postmedian line of forewing diagonal and clear comma like; hind wing median line very short, comma like and curved outside; anal tuft

ocherous yellow and also striped with white patches on both sides of anal extremity and descents to the end (Fig. 4). The female to male ratio was around 3:1.

The samples collected from *M. maximus* inflorescence revealed that the surface chemicals included 32 Compounds (Table 2). Amongst these,

Fig. 3. Male *C. medinalis* collected from inflorescence

Fig. 4. Female *C. medinalis* collected from inflorescence

corrinoids and n-(1-deoxy-1-fructosyl) serine were observed. McCutcheon et al. (2009) reported that in some insects corrinoids have an indirect effect by acting as an essential cofactor for obligate symbionts that provide key nutrients to the host. The chemical n-(1-deoxy-1-fructosyl) serine is an Amadori compound. Alaerjani et al. (2022) reported that Amadori products are formed in the early stage of millard reaction which includes a combination of sugars and amino groups. It implies the presence of fructose and serine in the surface chemicals. Li et al. (2021) found that the *C. medinalis* fed with fructose had shown an increase in longevity, total fecundity, oviposition period and oviposition rate, while net reproductive rate, intrinsic rate of increase and finite rate of increase were also significantly improved. In diamond back moth, *Plutella xylostella* (L) the adult fed with fructose had shown an increase in longevity, total fecundity, egg viability, oviposition period, oviposition rate and high intrinsic rate of increase (Marchioro et al., 2013). The insect

population fed with fructose increased eight times greater than the insects fed with distilled water in two generations. Takashi et al. (1980) reported that in case of female *C. medinalis* adults, ovarian maturation was accelerated by feeding on sugar. The sources of sugar in the fields were not known. Present study shows that *C. medinalis* could utilize substances present on surface of inflorescence of *M. maximus* as a source of its sugar in the field condition as evinced from the observation from the field.

The extract collected from the inflorescence for the identification of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) revealed the presence of 19 distinct compounds (Table 3). The GC-HRMS chromatogram of *M. maximus* is showed in Fig. 5. The identified volatile compounds belong to three categories: alkanes, esters, and ethers. Among these, bis (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate exhibited the highest peak intensity, followed by 4-methyldecane. Out of the 19 identified volatile compounds, six were recognized as potential attractants. These include bis (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, di-*n*-octyl phthalate, diisooctyl phthalate, 1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, dinonyl ester, 4-methyl decane and phthalic acid 6- ethyloct-3-yl-2-ethylhexyl ester (Fig. 6). In a study conducted by Sahayaraj (2008) the kairomone extract of tobacco caterpillar, *Spodoptera litura* (Fabricius) had di-*n*-octyl phthalate, diisooctyl phthalate, 4-methyl decane and bis (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate while in the kairomone extract of blister beetle, *Mylabris pustulata* (Thunberg) showed the presence of bis (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, diisooctyl phthalate. Liu et al. (2007) reported that in the honeydew of both silverleaf whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) on cabbage and greenhouse whitefly, *Trialeurodes*

Fig. 5. GC-HRMS chromatogram of Guinea grass inflorescence extract

Table 2. Compounds identified (LC-HRMS analysis) in surface chemicals of inflorescence extract

Compound name	Molecular formula	Retention time (min)	[m/z] +	[m/z]-	Class of compound
Ethyl 3-(methylthio) butanoate	C ₇ H ₁₄ O ₂ S	1.047	185.0620		Fatty acid ester
6-Feruloylcatalpol	C ₂₅ H ₃₀ O ₁₃	1.259		537.1667	Hydroxycinnamic acid
Benzoic acid	C ₇ H ₆ O ₂	1.273	123.0447		Aromatic carboxylic acid
Scutellarein 5,6,7,4'-tetramethyl ether	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₆	1.285	365.0992		Flavonoid
Hamamelose	C ₆ H ₁₂ O ₇	1.303		195.0505	Aldopentose
α-D-Galacturonic acid	C ₆ H ₁₀ O ₇	1.313		193.0346	Glucuronic acid derivative
1,4-beta-D-Glucan	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₁₈	1.370		535.1515	Beta-glucan
(+)-Mecambroline	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ NO ₃	1.403	318.1128		Aporphine alkaloid
(+)-threo-2-Amino-3,4-dihydroxybutanoic acid	C ₄ H ₉ NO ₄	1.554	136.0589		Alpha amino acid
Isolobinine	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ NO ₂	1.629	288.1977		Organooxygen compound
Floribundine	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₂	1.741	304.1337		Aporphine
Threonate	C ₄ H ₈ O ₅	1.771	137.0430		Sugar acids and derivative
(S)-3-Methylthiohexyl hexanoate	C ₁₃ H ₂₆ O ₂ S	1.784	269.1553		Fatty acid ester
Mirasan	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ CN ₂	1.847	241.1500		Monochlorobenzenes
Deidaclin	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO ₆	1.876		316.1032	Organooxygen compound
Medicanine	C ₇ H ₁₃ NO ₃	1.930	182.0771		Alpha amino acids
Oxaprozin	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₃	1.977	316.0938		Phenyl-1,3-oxazole
N-(1-Deoxy-1-fructosyl) serine	C ₉ H ₁₇ NO ₈	2.053	268.0989		Serine and derivatives
3beta,6beta-Dihydroxynortropane	C ₇ H ₁₃ NO ₂	3.156	166.0827		Tropane alkaloid
10-Hydroxyamitriptyline	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ NO	4.682	316.1697		Dibenzocycloheptenes
Methyl N- methylanthranilate	C ₉ H ₁₁ NO ₂	4.748	188.0664		Benzoic acid esters
L-Acetopine	C ₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄	5.361	233.1232		Alpha amino acid
Para- Trifluoromethylphenol	C ₇ H ₅ F ₃ O	5.460	163.0351		Organofluorine compound
Neamine (Neomycin A)	C ₁₂ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₆	5.673	323.1907		Aminoglycoside
Lysyl-Asparagine	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄	6.888	261.1544		Dipeptide
Corrinoid	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₄	7.473	307.1957		Tetrapyrrole
Bucharaine	C ₁₉ H ₂₅ NO ₄	7.754	332.1906		Quinolines
Edetate	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₈	13.041	315.0801		Tetracarboxylic acids and derivatives
8S-HODE	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₃	18.172		295.2271	Fatty Acyls
Ricinoleic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₃	18.438	321.2359		Fatty acid ester
N-Undecylbenzenesulfonic acid	C ₁₇ H ₂₈ O ₃ S	20.096		311.1682	Benzenesulfonic acids and derivatives
2-Dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O ₃ S	22.344		325.1837	Benzenesulfonic acids and derivatives

Table 3. Compounds identified (GC-HRMS analysis of inflorescence extract

Compound name	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Retention time (min)	Peak area (%)	Nature of compound
Phthalic acid, 6-ethyloct-3-yl 2-ethylhexyl ester	C ₂₆ H ₄₂ O ₄	418	34.08	2.58	Acid ester
1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, dinonyl ester	C ₂₆ H ₄₂ O ₄	418	34.13	2.41	Acid ester
Hexanedioic acid, mono (2-ethylhexyl)ester	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ O ₄	258	21.00	1.89	Acid ester
Adipic acid, 2-ethylhexyl pentadecyl ester	C ₂₉ H ₅₆ O ₄	468	24.31	1.20	Acid ester
Oxalic acid, 2-ethylhexyl nonyl ester	C ₁₉ H ₃₆ O ₄	328	34.36	3.10	Acid ester
1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, mono (2-ethylhexyl) ester	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄	278	34.49	1.55	Acid ester
1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, diundecyl ester	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O ₄	474	34.58	2.75	Acid ester
1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, diisodecyl ester	C ₂₈ H ₄₆ O ₄	446	34.76	3.62	Acid ester
Phthalic acid, dodecyl nonyl ester	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ O ₄	460	34.99	2.06	Acid ester
Phthalic acid, decyl nonyl ester	C ₂₇ H ₄₄ O ₄	432	35.03	2.24	Acid ester
4-methyldecane	C ₁₁ H ₂₄	156	29.39	13.10	Alkane
2,3-Dimethylnonane	C ₁₁ H ₂₄	156	25.44	1.20	Alkane
4,5-Dimethylundecane	C ₁₃ H ₂₈	184	26.67	3.27	Alkane
5,6-Dipropyldecane	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	226	30.59	9.82	Alkane
Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄	390	32.33	28.10	Ester
Diisooctyl phthalate	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄	390	33.72	8.27	Ester
Di-n-octyl phthalate	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄	390	33.17	6.55	Ester
Diocetyl ether	C ₁₆ H ₃₄ O	242	32.78	3.10	Ether
Methyl octyl ether	C ₉ H ₂₀ O	144	33.31	3.10	Ether

Fig. 6. Mass spectra of potential volatiles

a. Mass spectra of 1,2- Benzenedicarboxylic acid, dinonyl ester, b. Mass spectra of 4-methyldecane c. Mass spectra of Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, d. Mass spectra of Diisooctyl phthalate, e. Mass spectra of Di-n-octyl phthalate, f. Mass spectra of Phthalic acid, 6-ethyloct-3-yl 2-ethylhexyl ester

vaporariorum (Westwood) on cucumber is acting as a kairomone for host-searching parasitoids which had the presence of bis (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate. Ali and Wright (2020) elucidated that bis (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate was also found in response secondary metabolic compounds released by sunhemp plants to the egg deposition of corn earworm, *Helicoverpa zea* (boddie). According to Davidson (2023) bis (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate was produced due to leaf herbivory in jasmine ecosystem, which probably plays an important role in natural enemy attraction. Kacprzyk et al. (2021) isolated sex-differentiating substances from adult bodies of European spruce bark beetle, *Ips typographus* (L.) and six-toothed bark beetle, *Pityogenes chalcographus* (L.) which consisted of phthalic acid, 6-ethyl-oct-3-yl-2-ethylhexyl ester and referred them as a probable pheromone whereas Chamarthi et al. (2011) reported decane 4-methyl along with some other compounds acted as attractants and/or oviposition stimulants for sorghum shoot fly, *Atherigona soccata* (Rondani). A mixture of compounds has been reported in the trail pheromone in tropical fire ant, *Solenopsis geminata* (F.), di-*n*-octyl phthalate is one among them which could be synthesized artificially and used in integrated pest management to lure and mass trap the ants (Igwe and Offiong, 2015). A study done by Bala and Badder (2023) reported that di-*n*-octyl phthalate, 1,2-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, dinonyl ester plays an important role in sexual and social communications in insects, reptiles and mammals. From all these studies it is evident that 6 out of 19 volatiles identified had previously proven insect attractance by itself or in combination with some other chemicals.

Present study reveals that both male and female of *C. medinalis* are getting attracted to the inflorescence surface of *M. maximus* and also getting benefitted by feeding on it. Both of these phenomena are not been reported before. Our study reveals that attractant compounds in *M. maximus* inflorescence is not a single compound but a combination of compounds. However, it is necessary to conduct behavioural bioassays to validate the pheromonal functionality as well as to find the best combination ratio with maximum response. Also to verify the possibility of compounds to use as a lure and for mass trapping *C. medinalis* in IPM to reduce the harmful effects.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

HC designed the research, conducted experiments and prepared the manuscript. BR corrected manuscript and provided guidance. SNM analyzed the data.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest.

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